

A Association between vitamin D deficiency and Troponin T mutation in heart failure patients

Asociación entre deficiencia de vitamina D y mutación de troponina T en pacientes con insuficiencia cardiaca

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Abstract

The risk of cardiovascular disease in vitamin D deficiency patients is higher than the general population. Though traditionally associated with bone and mineral health, vitamin D has been proven to have a wide range of extraskeletal effects, including a function in intestinal calcium absorption and bone mineralization. These cells include a receptor for vitamin D (VDR) and 1-hydroxylase. Genetic forms of cardiomyopathy are caused predominantly by mutations in structural components of the cardiomyocyte sarcomeres, the contractile units of the heart, which includes cardiac Troponin T (TnT).

The aim of present study was evaluated if troponin T mutations affect vitamin D and increase the risk of cardiovascular disease. In 60 cardiovascular patients, these patients have Vitamin D deficiency; we tested the genetic mutations in troponin T with Vitamin D deficiency in Iraqi population by using specific PCR technique. The result showed that vitamin D deficiency could affect the cardiovascular diseases. On the other hand, genetic mutations in the troponin t could increase the risk of effect of vitamin D on heart failure HF.

Keywords: Troponin T(TNT), Vitamin D, Heart failure (HF), Cardiovascular disease (CVD).

Resumen

El riesgo de enfermedad cardiovascular en pacientes con deficiencia de vitamina D es mayor que en la población general. Aunque tradicionalmente se asocia con la salud ósea y mineral, se ha demostrado que la vitamina D tiene una amplia gama de efectos extraesqueléticos, incluida una función en la absorción intestinal de calcio y la mineralización ósea. Estas células incluyen un receptor de vitamina D (VDR) y 1-hidroxilasa. Las formas genéticas de miocardiopatía son causadas predominantemente por mutaciones en componentes estructurales de los sarcomeros de cardiomiocitos, las unidades contráctiles del corazón, que incluyen la troponina T cardíaca (TnT).

El objetivo del presente estudio fue evaluar si las mutaciones de troponina T afectan la vitamina D y aumentan el riesgo de enfermedad cardiovascular. En 60 pacientes cardiovasculares, estos pacientes tienen deficiencia de vitamina D; Probamos las mutaciones genéticas en la troponina T con deficiencia de vitamina D en la población iraquí mediante el uso de una técnica de PCR específica. El resultado mostró que la deficiencia de vitamina D podría afectar las enfermedades cardiovasculares. Por otra parte, las mutaciones genéticas en la troponina t podrían aumentar el riesgo de efecto de la vitamina D en la insuficiencia cardiaca IC.

Palabras clave: Troponina T (TNT), Vitamina D, Insuficiencia cardíaca (IC), Enfermedad cardiovascular (ECV).

Troponin is a protein that regulates heart muscle contraction¹. It is consisted of three proteins Troponin T, troponin I, and troponin C Cardiac troponins I and T are the recommended biomarkers for the diagnosis of acute myocardial infarction (AMI), according to the American Heart Association². The term “acute myocardial ischemia” This technique is used when there is cardiac necrosis indicating acute myocardial ischemia. A spike or drop in cardiac troponin (cTn) concentrations in the peripheral circulation with at least one value larger than the 95 % confidence interval of the upper reference limit are necessary to identify acute myocardial infarction³. The researchers observed that, after adjusting for cardiovascular disease risk factors, low 25(OH)D levels did not seem to be related to commonly occurring increased hscTnT levels^{4,5}. Previous cross-sectional studies evaluating the link between Vit D and cardiac troponin T or I levels have shown mixed findings. In patients with stable coronary artery disease, serum 25(OH)D levels are negatively related to cardiac troponin levels^{3,6}. High-sensitivity cardiac troponin T (hscTnT) is thought to be a biomarker for myocardial damage, wall stress, and other heart disorders⁷.

Low vitamin D levels may be linked to CHD or HF, however subclinical myocardial damage and wall stress may be linked to an intermediate phenotype^{8,9}. That said, early indications of myocardial damage and stress may signify a time at which therapies like vitamin supplementation may be useful in delaying development to clinical results¹⁰. The relationship between low vitamin D levels and subclinical myocardial injury and wall stress is unknown, however, evidence suggests they may be linked^{11,12}. Several previous cross-sectional investigations have shown inconsistent findings¹³.

From December 2020 to April 2021, 100 Iraqi patients (male and female) with various cardiovascular diseases were blood sampled at Hit General Hospital. The patient group (Group1) averaged (18-70). A disposable syringe was used to collect 4 ml of peripheral blood. After 15 minutes at 3000 RPM, serum was transferred to 2ml Eppendorf tubes and stored at -20oC for analysis. Also, 30 participants (25-55 years) were given blood samples to act as controls (Group 2).

The SYNCTM DNA Extraction Kit extracted total genomic DNA (Geneaid). Has been used to extract DNA from patients group (Group 1) and control group (Group 2). Nanodrop was used to test DNA purity and concentration. Then, to verify the sample’s DNA integrity, gel electrophoresis was utilized after extraction.

The second step was preparation of primers, we design forward primers and reverse primers for TNNI1 gene (Table 1). Microgen’s primer preparation instructions call for dissolving 300 mL of nuclease-free water into a lyophilized primer stock solution to get a concentration of 100 pmol/μL. The stock solution was then kept at -20° C until it was time to utilize it. After that Overlapping PCR technique has been used to get the human cardiac troponin T and tested by gel electrophoresis.

Table 1. Primer sequences utilized

Primer	Sequence		Size
TNNT1	R	5'- AGT TCT GAC ATA GAA GAG TGG -'3	669 b.P
	F	5'- CTA TTT CCA GCG CCC GGT GAC -'3	

Molecular studies

Juvenile and adult cardiomyopathies impair the heart muscles, causing early morbidity and death. Genes that code for cardiac Troponin T, a structural component of cardiomyocyte sarcomeres, cause genetic types of cardiomyopathy (TnT). This study aims to correlate the genetic mutations in troponin T with Vitamin D deficiency in the Iraqi population by a particular PCR technique.

Before utilizing PCR, agarose gel electrophoresis was used to assess the quality (3-1). Nanodrop quantified the genomic DNA’s concentration and quality.

Figure 1. DNA bands were visualized under UV after staining with EtBr on 1% agarose gel at 70 volts for 1 hour. DNA was isolated from the patient and control whole blood samples (1-5) and (6-10) respectively.

2PCR analysis for TNNI1 gene:

PCR amplified areas with a molecular weight of 696bp reflect the TNNT1 gene. The TNNT1 gene primers are used in the PCR process. Use of a 2000 bp DNA ladder to identify the PCR product

Figure 2. A snapshot of the PCR product for the TNNT gene stained with Red safe in 1.5 percent agarose gel at 200 volts for 1 hour, M: 2000 b.p DNA ladder, shows the PCR product for the TNNT gene, which is 669bp in length. The PCR product of the TNNT gene (669 bp) is shown in lanes 1 – 5 for controls, while the PCR product of the TNNT gene (669) is shown in lanes 6-19 for heart failure patients.

The use of DNA sequencing has considerably advanced biological and medical research¹⁴. The nucleic acid sequence—the order of nucleotides in DNA—was determined by DNA sequencing in this study. Therefore, all PCR products were verified by sequencing to test the PCR products for patients and controls. The result showed that the control group gave 98% similarity to the wild type of TnT gen while 60% of the patient group showed that there was a mutation in the TnT gen in position (204) as shown in figure 3.8.

Figure 3. Sanger sequencing results from PCR products of the TNNT gene

To detect the effect of the mutation in position 204, which was identified in 60% of patients, we used WebLogo3. According to the result of the sequencing (Figure 3.8), there is a genetic modification in the sequence of the TNN1 gene, and could this mutation affect the action of troponin T. Moreover, the alignment between human cardiac troponin T and 42 sequences (figure 3.9) showed that the position from 200 to 210 in the nucleic acid order of the TNN1 gene has a great impact on the structure of troponin T and results in altered function of troponin T. The question we need to understand is whether the mutations at a specific location of troponin T affect the metabolism of vitamin D. A recent study (6) explained alterations in Ca²⁺ dynamics, increased Ca²⁺ sensitivity, and contractility problems due to TnT mutations. This location is within the TNT1 region of the protein is essential for the function of the TnT protein^{15,16}. Earlier

studies reported that mutations in the region between amino acids 92–110 of TNNT2 impairs Tm binding or the ability of TnT to enhance tropomyosin-actin binding, leading to improper muscle contraction^{17,18}. Therefore, Mutations in TNT1 that alter its flexibility lead to changes in Ca²⁺ activation and Ca²⁺ sensitivity¹⁹. The regulatory element of Ca²⁺ is partially retained in the TNT2 domain of TnT; however, for regulation of contractility, Ca²⁺ needs Tm-TNT1 binding to propagate its signal²⁰. The changes in TNT1 flexibility promote Ca²⁺ alterations, which have been shown to correspond to Ca²⁺ sensitivity, where increased flexibility leads to increased Ca²⁺ sensitivity^{19,22}.

Figure 4. The alignment between human cardiac troponin T and 42 sequences. The figure shows the importance of amino acid of troponin T. The figure was obtained by Weblogo3

Conclusions

This study set out to investigate the effects of genetic mutations on troponin T if these mutations increase the risk of CVD with low level of Vitamin D. One unanticipated finding was that the mutation in position 204 in troponin T in 60% of patients. This sit in Troponin T according to many studies is fundamental on dynamic of Ca²⁺. In summary, we suggest that the mutation in TnT affects the ability of Tm to bind TnT, leading to changes in Ca²⁺ dynamics, increased Ca²⁺ sensitivity, and contractility defects. Diastolic function is dysregulated while EF is maintained. The atrium, in this case, is enlarged to relieve the pressure and promote the proper ventricular filling. At a point where the atrium is unable

to efficiently maintain the heart function, remodeling, involving increased collagen deposits and fibrosis, progresses ultimately leading to heart failure.

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